

DATA SPACE SELECTION GUIDE

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Table of content

Executive summary	4
1. Introduction	6
2. Basics of data ecosystems	7
2.1 Gaia-X	8
2.2 IDS	8
2.3 Flex4Res data space selection guide	9
3. Best practices on how to set up services and how to offer datasets	10
3.1 Choice of data space framework	11
3.2 Setting up services and datasets	11
3.3 Data source integration and connectors	12
3.4 Lessons learned	13
3.5 Overall insights and best practices	13
4. Examples from Flex4Res	14
4.1 Sidenor use case: IDS and Gaia-X implementation	14
4.2 Value stream assessment	16
5. Conclusion	17
6. References	18
7. Project partners	19
8. Contact	19

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AAS	Asset Administration Shell
DID	Decentralised Identifier
IDS	International Data Space
IDS-RAM	International Data Space Reference Architecture Model
IDSA	International Data Space Association
MPS	Master Production Scheduler
PoC	Penalty of Change
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
UC	Use Case
Verifiable Credential	VC
VSRAat	Value Stream Resilience Assessment tool

Executive summary

This whitepaper distills the experience of the Flex4Res project in designing, deploying and operating industrial data spaces, with a focus on resilience in manufacturing networks. It translates a diverse set of technical pilots and architectural concepts (Gaia-X, International Data Spaces (IDS), Pontus-X and Asset Administration Shell (AAS)) into practical guidance for organisations that want to share data and services securely while retaining sovereignty over sensitive production information.

The paper begins with the observation that most current cross-company digital services are implemented via centralised cloud platforms operated by a single provider. While convenient, this model struggles to satisfy manufacturing requirements for trust, sovereignty, regulatory compliance and transparent control of where data is stored and how it is used. In response, European initiatives such as the European Strategy for Data, Gaia-X and IDS have introduced the concepts of federated data spaces and broader data ecosystems as a basis for interoperable, cross-domain collaboration.

Building on these foundations, the whitepaper clarifies the relationship between data platforms, data spaces and data ecosystems and explains the core architectural elements needed for each. It summarises the Gaia-X Trust Framework (self-descriptions, verifiable credentials, decentralised identifiers and federated catalogues) and the IDS Reference Architecture (business, functional, process, information and system layers, underpinned by security, certification and governance). These frameworks provide the rules and building blocks for federated identity, policy-controlled data exchange and verifiable service execution.

To support decision-makers, the Flex4Res Data Space Selection Guide is introduced as a structured path for choosing an appropriate data-sharing model. A sequence of five questions, ranging from the use of remote Flex4Res services to intentions for data monetisation and available IT infrastructure, leads to one of five configurations: no data space (local-only), secure data sharing via IDS, data monetisation via Pontus-X or cloud/local compute-to-data setups using Pontus-X. This guide helps companies position themselves realistically in terms of technical readiness, business goals and governance needs.

The core of the whitepaper is a synthesis of best practices from four industrial use cases (Sidenor, GO-IMEK, Voestalpine, Hans Berg) that all implemented data spaces using Pontus-X, combined with Gaia-X and, in some instances, IDS:

- All cases converged on compute-to-data architectures, where algorithms and services are moved to the data rather than exporting sensitive datasets.
- Partners followed a pragmatic evolution from a fully manual setup (portal-based registration, manual metadata entry, ad-hoc deployment) towards partial automation (e.g., tools like Trident for DID generation and publication), while intentionally keeping governance tasks such as access control and metadata validation under human oversight.
- Data integration was realised via a mix of IDS connectors, Gaia-X-compliant components, Ocean Protocol elements within Pontus-X and factory-level connectors (e.g., OPC-UA). Harmonising metadata and aligning security policies across these layers proved more challenging than deploying pure technology.

The lessons learned are grouped into technical, organisational and procedural dimensions. Technically, early investment in metadata models, connector architecture and compute environments reduces the friction associated with downstream integration. Organisationally, clear IT and security policies, agreed governance rules and consistent documentation are critical for sustaining collaborative data spaces beyond pilot projects. Procedurally, an incremental strategy – starting with small, manually controlled prototypes and automating only once processes stabilise – helps balance agility with compliance.

Two detailed examples ground these insights. The Sidenor use case demonstrates how IDS and Gaia-X can be integrated with Pontus-X to coordinate planning and resilience services across multiple steel plants, without exposing raw production data, by utilising verifiable credentials, usage policies and auditable transactions. A second example illustrates how a value stream resilience assessment tool can operate in a Gaia-X-compliant compute-to-data environment, enabling external experts to analyse highly sensitive production data without compromising confidentiality.

The whitepaper concludes that successful data space deployment in manufacturing is less about choosing a single “perfect” platform and more about aligning governance, connector maturity and organisational readiness. Data spaces, when implemented with federated trust, compute-to-data principles and pragmatic automation, provide a concrete pathway to resilience assessment, reconfiguration strategies and new data-driven services across industrial ecosystems.

1. Introduction

The increasing digitalisation of manufacturing systems has intensified the demand for secure, transparent and sovereign mechanisms of data exchange across organisational boundaries. Conventional cloud-based platform models, typically operated by a single provider, have proven insufficient for industrial environments where sensitive production information, regulatory compliance and verifiable control over data usage are essential preconditions for collaboration. At the same time, emerging requirements related to resilience, distributed production coordination and cross-company service integration highlight the limitations of isolated data platforms and underscore the need for more federated and interoperable approaches. In response, the European strategy for data and initiatives such as Gaia-X and the IDS have introduced new architectural paradigms that aim to reconcile interoperability with sovereignty, enabling companies to participate in shared digital ecosystems without relinquishing control of their data assets.

Within this broader context, the Flex4Res project investigates how such federated data-sharing concepts can be operationalised in real industrial settings to support manufacturing resilience. The project explores how Gaia-X trust mechanisms, IDS connectors and compute-to-data environments, particularly those provided by the Pontus-X ecosystem, can be combined to enable policy-controlled data exchange and service execution across distributed production networks. Rather than focusing on abstract architectural models, the project emphasises practical implementation, including the onboarding of participants, the publication of datasets and services, the configuration of connectors and the design of governance processes for secure and traceable collaboration. Through four industrial use cases, the project demonstrates how federated data spaces can support tasks such as production scheduling, cross-site coordination, value-stream resilience assessment and the execution of advanced analytics without exposing sensitive operational information.

The purpose of this whitepaper is to consolidate these experiences and provide a structured account of the technical, organisational and procedural lessons learned during the design and deployment of data spaces within Flex4Res. The document outlines the conceptual foundations of data platforms, data spaces and data ecosystems, examines the practical challenges of integrating Gaia-X, IDS and Pontus-X components and distils best practices for setting up services, publishing datasets and managing compute-to-data interactions. In doing so, it seeks to offer practitioners, researchers and industrial stakeholders a realistic perspective on the maturity, opportunities and limitations of current dataspace technologies for enhancing resilience in manufacturing value chains.

2. Basics of data ecosystems

In today's cross-company implementations of digital twins and data-driven services, an infrastructure based on a platform model is typically employed. Such a data platform is composed of multiple interconnected elements, including components, roles, processes, relationships and interfaces. These elements are designed within a cohesive architectural framework that underpins an organisation's products and services while accommodating diverse customer requirements (Strnadl & Schöning, 2023a). In this approach, a single organisation generally provides a centralised cloud infrastructure that coordinates all data and information exchange. However, for the manufacturing industry, relying on an external cloud platform often fails to meet critical needs for trust, data sovereignty, transparency, and security, as the data frequently contains sensitive intellectual property. Furthermore, these requirements encompass the traceable verification of where data is stored and how it is used, ensuring compliance with relevant legal and regulatory standards.

Figure 1: Difference between data platforms, data spaces and data ecosystems

To address these limitations and foster interoperability across various domains and infrastructures, the European strategy for data has introduced the concepts of data spaces and data ecosystems (COM/2020/66, n.d.). A data space can be defined as “a coordinated set of standards, organizational policies, and data space services operating under a specified governance model to enable and facilitate data exchange among participants” (Bitkom_Data_Act_Position_Paper_July22_Cloud_13.07.22.Pdf, n.d.). Its fundamental services include identity and access management, audit logging and connectors that enable interaction between participants.

Conversely, a data ecosystem represents a broader and more flexible construct, described as “the alignment structure of a multilateral group of partners that collaborate to realise a shared value proposition” (Strnadl & Schöning, 2023b). Consequently, while an ecosystem may encompass one or more data spaces, it is not limited to data exchange, does not rely exclusively on connectors and may function with less stringent governance structures. The three related concepts – data platform, data space and data ecosystem – along with their respective lead concepts, are depicted in Figure 1.

2.1 Gaia-X

The Gaia-X initiative [<https://gaia-x.eu/gaia-x-framework/>] was launched in 2019 as a joint project between the German and French Ministries of Economic Affairs and is now managed by the Gaia-X European Association for Data and Cloud AISBL. This organisation defines specifications for a federated and secure data infrastructure, aiming to connect currently fragmented data and infrastructure ecosystems.

According to the Gaia-X Trust Framework (Gaia-X Trust Framework - 22.10 Release, n.d.), participation in a Gaia-X-compliant data space or ecosystem requires three essential components. First, each provider must be described through Gaia-X Credentials based on W3C standards for Verifiable Credentials (VCs) and Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) (Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) v1.0, n.d.). These credentials include a notarised legal registration number, a self-description with headquarters details and acceptance of the Gaia-X Terms & Conditions, all represented in JSON-LD format. Second, the offered asset—such as a digital twin, Asset Administration Shell (AAS) or service—must be described as a structured resource linked to the provider's identity. Finally, both descriptions are combined into a verifiable presentation, validated by a digital clearing house, and published in a federated catalogue, allowing other participants to discover and contract the offering.

Since the implementation details of data spaces differ, interoperability is achieved through adaptable software components that convert and extend offerings to match the requirements of specific ecosystems (Gast et al., 2024). For instance, Pontus-X relies on distributed ledger technology, which necessitates additional information such as blockchain account identifiers and token references.

2.2 IDS

The IDS initiative originated as the Industrial Data Space programme by Fraunhofer to establish a secure and trusted framework for data sharing between organisations. It evolved into the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), a non-profit organisation promoting global standardisation of data sovereignty and interoperability across industries. The initiative's goal is to enable companies to exchange and use data securely while maintaining full control over their information. Founded in Germany, IDS has strong ties with Plattform Industrie 4.0 and collaborates with initiatives such as the Big Data Value Association, FIWARE Foundation and OPC Foundation to create a federated data infrastructure.

The IDS Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM) defines the key pillars of this ecosystem through a five-layer architecture supported by three overarching perspectives: Security, certification and governance. The Business Layer defines the roles and interactions of participants; the Functional Layer specifies system requirements such as trust, security and interoperability; the Process Layer models dynamic interactions like onboarding and data exchange; the Information Layer structures data semantics via a shared ontology; and the System Layer handles component integration and deployment. Together, these pillars ensure a decentralised, trusted and standardised environment for secure data exchange and data sovereignty across organisational boundaries (IDS Reference Architecture Model 3.0, n.d.).

2.3 Flex4Res data space selection guide

The Flex4Res Data Space Selection Guide was designed to help use cases navigate different options for sharing and accessing data and services in the context of advanced manufacturing and Industry 4.0. It was first introduced in the deliverable “D2.2 – Flex4Res Data Spaces Framework for Reconfigurable Value Chain (2nd version)” and it provides a structured approach for selecting the most suitable data-sharing model based on the technical, business, and infrastructural capabilities of each use case. The overall process is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Data space selection guide

The guide follows a five-step decision path:

1. Does the use case intend to use a Flex4Res remotely deployed service?
2. Can the use case share manufacturing data through a data space?
3. Is the use case's goal to monetise data sharing in the near future?
4. Does the use case have the required IT infrastructure?
5. Can the use case deploy project services in its own environment?

Based on these questions, each use case can identify one of five possible configurations for interacting with the Flex4Res ecosystem:

- **Data spaces are not applicable:** In this scenario, the company operates entirely with local services and AAS, without the need for external data exchange or shared project services. This is suitable for organisations focusing purely on internal optimisation.
- **Exchange data using IDS:** For companies ready to share data securely and in compliance with industrial standards, the IDS framework provides a trusted mechanism for exchanging information across manufacturing partners. IDS enables controlled, rule-based data sharing under agreed conditions to

support collaboration, efficiency improvements and compliance. Although IDS foresees future mechanisms for data monetisation, such as data marketplaces, these components are not yet fully available. Therefore, in the current phase, IDS serves mainly for collaborative and secure data exchange rather than direct commercialisation.

- Sell data using Pontus-X: When the strategic goal is to monetise manufacturing data, Pontus-X offers the capability to upload and sell datasets through a secure, standardised platform. This approach allows companies to explore new business models by transforming operational data into valuable digital assets.
- Share services using Pontus-X in Cloud Compute-to-Data: In cases where local IT infrastructure is limited or unavailable, services can be deployed in the cloud using the Pontus-X Compute-to-Data environment. Here, data and computation are handled remotely and project services are accessed through a cloud-based setup, ensuring flexibility and scalability without requiring on-premise hardware.
- Share services using Pontus-X in Local Compute-to-Data: For use cases with sufficient IT infrastructure, services can be deployed locally within the company's environment. This setup allows data to remain on-premise while computations occur securely within the same environment. It provides the highest level of control, data sovereignty and customisation, aligning with companies that prioritise security and compliance.

Through these five pathways, the guide supports decision-makers in assessing their digital readiness, identifying their collaboration objectives and selecting the most suitable approach for integrating into the Flex4Res data space ecosystem. The updated structure, reflecting the clarified question on data monetisation and the extended description of IDS, is illustrated in Figure 2.

3. Best practices on how to set up services and how to offer datasets

The integration of services and datasets into data spaces is central to enabling secure and interoperable data exchange across industrial ecosystems. Within the examined use cases (UC1–UC4), partners explored various approaches to deploying data spaces using the Pontus-X platform under the Gaia-X and, in some cases, the IDS framework.

While all use cases shared the same foundational technologies, their experiences reveal differences in motivation, process maturity, automation and integration strategies. The following sections summarise the setup practices and lessons learned from each of these.

3.1 Choice of data space framework

All use cases adopted Pontus-X as the primary data space environment, often complemented by Gaia-X and IDS components to enforce trusted, policy-controlled data sharing.

UC1 (Sidenor) integrated IDS and Gaia-X to enable secure, policy-driven data exchange within the steel manufacturing sector. Pontus-X served as the compute-to-data bridge, allowing local service execution without transferring sensitive data outside the company's boundaries. The need for federated trust, compliance verification and complete data sovereignty across distributed production sites drove the decision.

UC2 (GOIMEK) chose Pontus-X because it aligned with the use case's compute-to-data requirements and offered straightforward integration via Ocean Protocol components. Although there was an initial learning curve, the framework provided support for iterative improvement and flexibility during deployment.

UC3 (Voestalpine) adopted Pontus-X as part of the Flex4Res hybrid architecture, which combines Gaia-X, IDS and AAS principles. This approach provided secure and standardised data exchange across industrial partners. The main trade-offs were the immaturity of manufacturing data spaces and the ongoing challenges of standardisation for AAS-based Digital Twins.

UC4 (Hans Berg) selected Pontus-X following project requirements to ensure Gaia-X compliance and local compute capabilities. The decision was also influenced by the need to avoid transferring live manufacturing data, favouring privately hosted services and Docker-based deployments within secure infrastructures.

Across all cases, partners faced a steep learning curve and varying levels of ecosystem maturity but found Pontus-X effective for establishing interoperable and secure data collaboration environments.

3.2 Setting up services and datasets

All partners followed a progression from manual setup to partial automation, striking a balance between efficiency and governance control.

UC1 deployed multiple production and resilience services, such as scheduling and supply-chain assessment, within local compute environments. Services were executed through Pontus-X using the Nautilus wrapper for Ocean.js and Docker containers, ensuring data never left the local infrastructure.

UC2 began with fully manual publication of datasets and services via the Pontus-X portal. Algorithm execution was later automated, while metadata creation and access control remained manual to preserve transparency and flexibility.

UC3 utilised the Trident tool, developed to automate the publication of datasets and algorithms within Pontus-X. It handled DID generation, testing and integration while partners retained manual oversight for metadata and access configuration.

UC4 followed the procedural steps defined in internal project deliverables, manually setting up services without the use of automation. This ensured controlled deployment while the infrastructure matured.

Overall, a hybrid approach proved most effective: automation for technical tasks such as deployment and testing, paired with manual governance for data control and compliance assurance.

3.3 Data source integration and connectors

Integration strategies differed according to technical constraints and data sensitivity.

UC1 implemented a hybrid architecture combining IDS, Gaia-X and Pontus-X. IDS components (Connectors, Broker, Clearing House) governed secure exchanges, Gaia-X Core Services verified participants and Pontus-X provided the compute-to-data bridge for local service execution. This ensured cross-site collaboration with full data sovereignty.

UC2 integrated Ocean Protocol components directly within Pontus-X instead of IDS connectors, leveraging the platform's built-in mechanisms for dataset management and algorithm execution. This streamlined integration was well-suited to its compute-to-data focus.

UC3 used both standardised and custom-built connectors. Gaia-X and IDS connectors enabled secure, federated data exchange, while the Trident connector simplified publication and pipeline integration. At the factory level, OPC-UA extensions and edge device integrations supported machine-level data acquisition.

UC4 relied on the Gaia-X-compliant Pontus-X connector model, using Docker-hosted services and local AAS middleware for communication. The primary integration challenge involved configuring DIMOFAC and maintaining Docker image hosting.

Common difficulties across cases included metadata harmonisation between AAS, IDS and Gaia-X layers, as well as aligning security policies between local and federated systems.

3.4 Lessons learned

Technical lessons

- Early attention to metadata modelling and compute setup reduces later integration issues.
- Modular connector architectures improve scalability and maintainability.
- Real-time data pipelines enhance responsiveness compared to static data uploads.

Organisational lessons

- Clear IT and security policies are essential for compute-to-data operations.
- Early alignment among partners on data governance and access rights prevents procedural delays.
- Consistent documentation ensures reproducibility and knowledge transfer.

Procedural lessons

- Begin with manual prototypes, then automate as workflows stabilise.
- Maintain manual oversight on metadata and access control until governance models mature.
- Develop shared templates and onboarding guides for consistent deployment across partners.

3.5 Overall insights and best practices

The four use cases demonstrate a collective shift from exploratory, manually configured setups to structured, semi-automated data space workflows. Pontus-X, complemented by Gaia-X and IDS components, proved a viable foundation for secure and interoperable collaboration.

UC1 showcased the benefits of combining IDS, Gaia-X and compute-to-data mechanisms for federated manufacturing coordination.

UC2 and UC4 highlighted the value of gradual automation, striking a balance between efficiency and governance.

UC3 demonstrated the potential of hybrid architectures and tooling, such as Trident, for scalable and standardised integration.

Together, these experiences reveal that success in data space deployment depends less on platform selection than on clarity of governance, maturity of connectors and organisational readiness. As data spaces evolve, combining technical standardisation with operational flexibility will remain key to offering datasets and services securely and sustainably across industrial ecosystems.

4. Examples from Flex4Res

This section presents two examples illustrating the use of IDS and Gaia-X data spaces. The first example demonstrates a combined approach, where IDS and Gaia-X data spaces are integrated to enable seamless data exchange within a Compute-to-Data environment, bridging the two ecosystems. The second example focuses on the implementation and practical application of a Gaia-X-compliant data space, demonstrating how it can facilitate secure and interoperable data sharing in industrial contexts.

4.1 Sidenor use case: IDS and Gaia-X implementation

Figure 3: Sidenor use case: IDS & Gaia-X data spaces

The Sidenor use case demonstrates how Flex4Res integrated IDS and Gaia-X to enable secure, policy-driven data sharing and service execution within the steel manufacturing sector – see Figure 3. Sidenor operates a network of steel plants across different countries, each producing a wide range of steel products for industrial and construction applications. The distributed nature of its operations, combined with volatile market conditions and regulatory constraints, creates a strong need for a secure and coordinated data-sharing mechanism to enhance resilience and responsiveness across its value chain.

Traditionally, Sidenor’s planning and scheduling activities were performed independently at each facility, using data extracted from a centralised ERP system. This approach caused inefficiencies such as delays in responding to disruptions, limited visibility across sites and high dependency on manual coordination.

Furthermore, due to the highly confidential nature of production and demand data, the company could not rely on conventional cloud-based solutions that required transferring sensitive data outside its internal network.

To address these challenges, Flex4Res framework was implemented using IDS for secure and policy-controlled data exchange and Gaia-X for federated trust and compliance management. In this architecture:

- The IDS components (including IDS Connectors, Broker and Clearing House) manage trusted data exchange between plants and external partners. All data transactions are encrypted, logged and governed by data usage contracts.
- The Gaia-X layer provides identity and compliance verification through Self-Descriptions, Verifiable Credentials and Gaia-X Core Services (Registry, Notary and Compliance Service). These ensure that both organisations and services participating in the data exchange are verified and operate according to defined policies.
- The Compute-to-Data environment, implemented via Pontus-X, serves as the bridge between IDS and Gaia-X. It allows services to be executed close to the data, either locally within Sidenor's infrastructure or in a trusted cloud environment, without requiring sensitive data to leave its origin.

Within this setup, several production and resilience-related services were deployed:

- The Master Production Scheduler (MPS) operates as an IDS service, accessing ERP data to generate a unified supply chain plan.
- A Supply Chain Resilience Assessment service evaluates this plan using the Penalty of Change (PoC) methodology to identify robust configurations that can better absorb disruptions.
- At the factory level, Production Planning and Production Scheduling services are downloaded and deployed through Pontus-X using Nautilus (a TypeScript wrapper for Ocean.js), running as Docker containers within local compute environments. These services adapt production schedules according to real-time constraints and data from machines or local databases.
- A Factory-Level Resilience Assessment is conducted using local PoC analysis to quantify the impact of disruptions such as equipment failure or supply shortages.

Through this combination of IDS and Gaia-X, Sidenor achieved a balance between data sovereignty and collaborative intelligence. External services could operate on Sidenor's data without direct access, while all interactions remained traceable and policy compliant. This setup allowed cross-plant coordination, faster decision-making under disruptions and improved alignment between enterprise-level and factory-level operations.

Technically, the IDS infrastructure relied on FIWARE TRUE Connectors for enforcing data usage policies, the Fraunhofer AISEC omejdn-server for identity management and IDS Clearing House for auditing transactions. On the Gaia-X side, the Pontus-X ecosystem provided the federated catalogue and compute environments through the Ocean Enterprise Connector, enabling verifiable execution of services.

The Sidenor use case validated the feasibility of the Flex4Res approach, showing that resilient manufacturing can be achieved through distributed, trusted data sharing and localised service deployment. By bridging IDS and Gaia-X, the framework demonstrated how steel manufacturers can securely connect their digital twins, ERP data and scheduling services while ensuring full control over sensitive operational information.

4.2 Value stream assessment

The value stream assessment demonstrates how sensitive data can be handled via the Gaia-X compute to data environment. Considering increasing uncertainties and disruptions in global supply chains and production processes, the ability of companies to respond flexibly and robustly to changing conditions is becoming ever more critical for long-term competitiveness. The study shows that resilience can be most effectively influenced by the responsible actors within the companies themselves. However, a fundamental prerequisite for this is the systematic assessment of the current level of resilience.

The findings indicate the need for a sound and practice-oriented approach that enables objective evaluation and the identification of potential weaknesses in production systems. PTW has developed the Value Stream Resilience Assessment tool (VSRAt) for assessing the resilience of value streams. The aim of this tool is to systematically analyse and evaluate the resilience of industrial production processes. However, data collected during a value stream assessment is generally highly sensitive for businesses. Any leakage of such information can be detrimental to the success of a company. At the same time, the personnel conducting the VSRA are often not part of the company itself but work for an external service provider such as a consulting firm. Until now, organisations have taken cumbersome measures to protect their proprietary knowledge, typically relying on NDAs or, in some cases, withholding important information from the VSRA, which in turn distorts the results.

Therefore, we use the Pontus-X data space. The VSRAt algorithm has been integrated as a compute-to-data solution, allowing users to download and execute the algorithm locally without sharing any sensitive data with the service provider. The corresponding architecture is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Value stream analysis in the Gaia-X context

5. Conclusion

The Flex4Res project demonstrates that data spaces implemented through Gaia-X, IDS and Pontus-X offer a viable foundation for secure, sovereign and interoperable collaboration across manufacturing networks. By combining federated trust mechanisms with compute-to-data principles, companies can share services, run advanced analytics and coordinate value-chain resilience without exposing sensitive operational data.

Across all examined use cases, success depended less on selecting a single framework and more on aligning governance structures, metadata models and connector maturity with organisational readiness. A gradual shift from manually controlled prototypes to semi-automated deployment pipelines proved effective, balancing agility with compliance needs. Ultimately, data spaces provide a structured pathway to scalable resilience assessment, reconfiguration strategies and new data-driven business models in industrial ecosystems.

Looking ahead, several opportunities emerge for advancing industrial data spaces. A key question is how governance models can be further harmonised to reduce complexity while still allowing companies to maintain full sovereignty. Likewise, expanding automation – especially for metadata validation, onboarding and credential management – opens the door to more scalable and user-friendly deployments. There is also significant potential in improving interoperability between Gaia-X, IDS, AAS and Pontus-X so that future data spaces can be integrated with less effort, particularly for SMEs.

In addition, compute-to-data architectures invite exploration of new business models beyond classic data monetisation, potentially enabling novel service marketplaces or federated analytics offerings. Finally, embedding resilience metrics directly into data space services could transform today's periodic resilience checks into continuous, data-driven improvement loops.

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